

A Prospective Study to Evaluate the Risk Factors and Effectiveness of Management Strategies in Postpartum Hemorrhage

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Abstract:

Introduction: Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly in low-resource settings where access to quality obstetric care is limited. Uterine atony is the primary cause of PPH, accounting for most cases, especially in developing countries. Early identification of risk factors and timely intervention are crucial to preventing severe outcomes. This study aims to evaluate the risk factors associated with PPH and assess the effectiveness of different management strategies in reducing morbidity and mortality.

Materials and Methods: This prospective study was conducted at Shri M. P. Shah Medical College, Jamnagar, from November 2022 to November 2023, including 52 patients diagnosed with PPH. Patients were identified through hospital admissions and referrals from surrounding health centers. Data were collected through patient interviews, medical records, and clinical observations, focusing on obstetric history and known risk factors such as prolonged labor and multiple gestations. Management strategies, including medical treatments, uterine massage, surgical interventions, and blood transfusions, were evaluated for effectiveness based on patient outcomes.

Results: In our study, 71.43% of patients were multiparous, and most (71.43%) were aged 24-30 years. Anemia was the most common high-risk factor (30.15%), followed by prolonged labor (12.69%) and preeclampsia/eclampsia (6.34%). Atonic PPH was the leading cause (52.70%), with traumatic causes like cervicovaginal tears at 28.38%. Medical management was the most frequently used treatment (38.10%), followed by uterine packing (25.40%) and vessel ligation (12.70%), with obstetric hysterectomy reserved for severe cases (6.35%).

Conclusion: The prevalence of multiparity and anemia as key risk factors for postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), with atonic PPH being the most common cause. Early identification and a stepwise management approach, starting with medical interventions, are essential in improving outcomes for affected patients.

Keywords: Postpartum hemorrhage, multiparity, anemia, uterine atony, medical management.

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Introduction

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality worldwide, significantly contributing to maternal deaths, particularly in low-resource settings. [1] The third stage of labor, which follows the delivery of the baby, is a critical period when unexpected and severe complications, such as PPH, can occur even after an otherwise normal labor and delivery process. [2] Globally, obstetric hemorrhage accounts for approximately 38% of maternal deaths, with PPH alone responsible for 25% of these fatalities. This translates to a staggering reality where around 1,600 women die each day

due to childbirth-related causes, with approximately 500 of these deaths attributed to PPH. [3] The leading cause of PPH is uterine atony, which is particularly prevalent in developing countries, where over 99% of PPH-related deaths occur. The incidence of PPH is reported to be between 2% and 4% following vaginal delivery and about 6% after cesarean section. [4] In middle and low-income countries, where access to quality obstetric care may be limited, the risk of death from PPH is considerably higher. For instance, in India, the maternal mortality rate remains unexpectedly high at 540 per 100,000 live births, underscoring

the urgent need for effective management strategies. [5] Clinically, PPH is defined as blood loss from the genital tract following delivery, regardless of the amount, that leads to hemodynamic instability, with symptoms like tachycardia and hypotension. [6] It can also be indicated by a hematocrit drop of 10% or hemorrhage requiring immediate transfusion. Average blood loss varies by delivery type, with 500 mL for vaginal delivery, 1 liter after cesarean section, and 1.5 liters following a cesarean hysterectomy. [7]

The purpose of this study is to identify, enumerate, and determine the frequency of risk factors associated with postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) and to evaluate the effectiveness of various management strategies. The goal is to achieve a significant reduction in hospital stay duration and to mitigate the long-term psychological impact of PPH on affected women.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Shri M. P. Shah Medical College, Jamnagar, over a one-year period from November 2022 to November 2023. The study aimed to assess the risk factors, management strategies, and outcomes associated with postpartum hemorrhage (PPH). During this period, a total of 52 patients who were diagnosed with PPH were included in the study.

The study population comprised all patients admitted primarily to the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, as well as those referred from primary and community health centers in nearby areas. The inclusion criteria ensured that all cases of PPH within the catchment area were included, providing a comprehensive dataset for analysis.

Data were collected through a combination of patient interviews, medical records review, and

clinical observations. Detailed patient histories were obtained, including obstetric history, pre-existing medical conditions, antenatal care, and any complications during pregnancy or labor. Specific attention was given to identifying known risk factors for PPH, such as prolonged labor, multiple gestations, and previous history of PPH. The diagnosis of PPH was established based on the visual estimation of blood loss exceeding 500 mL following vaginal delivery, or 1,000 mL following cesarean section. In addition to visual estimation, clinical signs of hemodynamic instability—such as tachycardia, hypotension, and signs of hemorrhagic shock—were used to confirm the diagnosis. Hematocrit levels were also monitored to assess the degree of blood loss and the need for transfusion. Management strategies employed during the study included uterotonic medications, manual uterine massage, surgical interventions (such as uterine artery ligation or hysterectomy), and blood transfusions. The effectiveness of these strategies was evaluated based on patient outcomes, including the duration of hospital stay, the need for intensive care, and overall recovery.

Data were analyzed to determine the frequency of various risk factors and to evaluate the relative effectiveness of the different management strategies. The study's findings aim to contribute to improved clinical guidelines and protocols for the management of PPH, with the goal of reducing maternal morbidity and mortality associated with this condition.

Results

In our study, the majority of the patients were multipara, accounting for 71.43% (45 patients), while primipara women constituted 28.57% (18 patients). This distribution reflects a higher incidence of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) in multipara women, suggesting that parity may be a potential risk factor for PPH.

Table 1: Distribution According to Parity

Parity	Number (Primipara)	Percentage (%)
Primipara	18	28.57%
Multipara	45	71.42%

The age distribution of patients in our study shows that the majority, 71.43% (45 patients), were between the ages of 24-30, with smaller percentages in the other age groups: 12.70% (8 patients) each for the 20-23 and >30 age groups,

and 3.17% (2 patients) for those under 20. This indicates that PPH is more prevalent in women aged 24-30, which may be related to the increased likelihood of deliveries and associated complications in this age group.

Table 2: Age Distribution of Patients

Age Group	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
<20	2	3.17%
20-23	8	12.69%
24-30	45	71.42%
>30	8	12.69%

Among those with high-risk factors, anemia was the most prevalent (20%), followed by preeclampsia/eclampsia (7%), prolonged labor/obstructed labor (6%), and twins/polyhydramnios (2%). These findings underscore the importance of vigilance across various demographic groups, particularly multiparous women and those in their mid to late twenties, for the early detection and management of PPH. In our study, 47.61% of patients presented with no identifiable high-risk factor, indicating that

postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) can occur unexpectedly. Anemia was the most prevalent high-risk factor, found in 30.15% of patients, followed by prolonged or obstructed labor at 12.69%. Less common factors included preeclampsia/eclampsia (6.34%) and twins/polyhydramnios (3.17%). These findings underscore the importance of careful monitoring and proactive management, particularly in patients with anemia or labor complications, to mitigate the risk of PPH.

Figure 1: Presence of High-Risk Factors (%)

In our study, the majority of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) cases were atonic in nature, accounting for 52.70% of the cases, reflecting the well-known role of uterine atony as the leading cause of PPH. Traumatic causes were significant, with cervicovaginal tears present in 28.38% of cases, and less frequently, vulval hematoma

(1.35%), pelvic hematoma (2.70%), and uterine rupture (5.41%).

Coagulation defects were responsible for 8.11% of cases, while mixed etiology was observed in 1.35% of cases.

Table 3: Distribution According to Etiology

Etiology	Number	Percentage (%)
Atonic	39	52.70%
Traumatic (20%)		
1. Cervicovaginal tear	21	28.38%
2. Vulval hematoma	1	1.35%
3. Pelvic hematoma	2	2.70%
4. Rupture of uterus	4	5.41%
Coagulation defects	6	8.11%
Mixed	1	1.35%

In our study, medical management was the most frequently used method for controlling postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), employed in 38.10% of cases. Uterine packing was the next most common approach, used in 25.40% of patients, followed by

vessel ligation in 12.70%. Bimanual uterine compression was performed in 9.52% of cases, while compression sutures were used in 7.94%. Obstetric hysterectomy, considered a last resort, was necessary in 6.35% of cases.

Table 4: Different method of management

Different method of management	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Medical management	24	38.10%
Bimanual uterus compression	6	9.52%
Compression suture	5	7.94%
Vessel ligation (b/l uterine, ovarian, internal iliac)	8	12.70%
Obstetric hysterectomy	4	6.35%
Uterine packing	16	25.40%

Discussion

In our study, multiparity was a significant risk factor for postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), with 71.43% of the patients being multipara, similar to findings from Briley et al. [8], where multiparity without cesarean section was associated with an increased risk of PPH progression. This is consistent with Buzaglo et al. [9], who reported that multiparity was once thought to be a risk factor, although it was not significant in their study. Meanwhile, Biguzzi et al. [10] identified other maternal factors such as nulliparity and episiotomy as significant risk factors for PPH, highlighting the multifactorial nature of PPH. Lastly, Nyfløt et al. [11] emphasized multiparity as a risk factor for severe PPH, which aligns with our findings that multiparity may increase the risk of PPH. This comparative analysis underlines the need for careful monitoring of multipara women to mitigate PPH risks.

In our study, the majority of patients (71.43%) were aged 24-30 years, which aligns with the findings of Fukami et al. [12], where younger maternal age was associated with increased risks of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), although their study also highlighted higher risks among older age groups. Similarly, the study by Ngwenya et al. [1] found that the mean age of women experiencing PPH was 27.7 years, emphasizing the prevalence of PPH in younger women. Additionally, Davey et al. [13] noted that older maternal age, specifically those above 35, was a significant risk factor for severe PPH. While our data focuses on the 24-30 age group, these comparative findings underline that age, both younger and older, plays a crucial role in the risk for PPH, necessitating age-tailored preventive strategies.

In our study, 47.61% of patients presented with no identifiable high-risk factor, consistent with findings from Fukami et al. [12], who reported that 20% of PPH cases occurred in women with no risk factors, highlighting the unpredictable nature of PPH. Anemia, the most prevalent high-risk factor in our study (30.15%), is similarly noted by Ngwenya et al. [1] as a common contributor to PPH, particularly in low-resource settings. Prolonged labor, which contributed to 12.69% of our cases, aligns with Butwick et al. [14], who identified prolonged labor as a significant risk factor for severe PPH. Additionally, preeclampsia/eclampsia

(6.34%) and twins/polyhydramnios (3.17%) were less common but important factors, as echoed by Davey et al. [13], who also emphasized the heightened risks associated with hypertensive disorders and multiple pregnancies. These comparisons underscore the need for proactive monitoring across diverse risk profiles to mitigate the risk of PPH. In our study, atonic postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) was the leading cause, accounting for 52.70% of cases, which aligns with findings from Biguzzi et al. [8], where uterine atony was a major cause of PPH, contributing to 70-90% of cases. Similarly, Briley et al. [8] and Buzaglo et al. [9] emphasize uterine atony as a significant factor in PPH cases, particularly in women without identifiable risk factors. Traumatic causes such as cervicovaginal tears, which accounted for 28.38% in our study, were also highlighted in Fukami et al. [12], where perineal lacerations were associated with increased PPH risk. Less frequent causes like coagulation defects, responsible for 8.11% in our study, were also noted by Davey et al. [13] and Butwick et al. as contributing factors, underscoring the multifactorial nature of PPH etiology and the need for individualized risk management approaches.

In our study, medical management was the most frequently utilized method for managing postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), employed in 38.10% of cases. This mirrors findings from Fukami et al. [12], who noted that first-line uterotonic medications such as oxytocin and misoprostol are widely used as primary interventions due to their effectiveness in promoting uterine contractions and reducing atonic hemorrhage. Briley et al. [8] also reported similar trends, where pharmacological management was emphasized as the initial step in controlling PPH. The prominence of medical management is likely due to its accessibility and relatively low invasiveness compared to surgical options. However, in cases where medical interventions fail, more invasive measures such as uterine packing, which was used in 25.40% of our patients, become necessary. Studies by Ngwenya [1] and Davey et al. [13] noted that uterine packing is frequently employed in low-resource settings, where rapid, minimally invasive control of bleeding is critical before proceeding to surgical interventions. Surgical interventions, including vessel ligation (12.70%) and compression sutures (7.94%), were

also necessary for more severe cases in our study, similar to reports by Biguzzi et al. [10], who found that surgical management is essential when medical treatments are insufficient. Bimanual uterine compression (9.52%) was used as a temporizing measure while preparing for more definitive management, a practice also observed in Buzaglo et al. [9], where mechanical methods were combined with medical approaches. Lastly, obstetric hysterectomy, used in 6.35% of our cases, remains a life-saving but drastic measure when other methods fail, as echoed by Butwick et al. [14], who noted that hysterectomy is often reserved for severe, refractory cases, particularly in high-risk patients with multiple complications. These findings emphasize the layered approach to PPH management, starting with less invasive options and escalating to surgical interventions based on the severity and response to initial treatments.

One limitation of our study is the reliance on visual estimation of blood loss, which can lead to inaccuracies in diagnosing the severity of postpartum hemorrhage (PPH). Additionally, the availability of interventions such as surgical methods may vary between settings, potentially influencing management choices. The study also focuses primarily on short-term outcomes, limiting our ability to assess long-term complications of PPH. Furthermore, the relatively small sample size may affect the generalizability of the findings to broader populations or different healthcare environments.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study highlights the importance of a stepwise approach in managing postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), with medical management being the most common and first-line intervention, followed by more invasive techniques such as uterine packing, vessel ligation, and compression sutures when necessary. The use of bimanual uterine compression as a temporary measure and the reliance on obstetric hysterectomy in the most severe, unresponsive cases underscores the need for flexible and resource-dependent strategies.

These findings align with other studies that emphasize the effectiveness of medical management while recognizing the critical role of surgical interventions when initial treatments fail, reinforcing the need for timely, individualized care to prevent maternal morbidity and mortality.

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